

Analgesic Optimization with Intravenous Lidocaine in a Diabetic Patient Undergoing Supracondylar Amputation: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Postoperative pain following major amputations represents a significant clinical challenge and is associated with increased morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, and a higher risk of chronic and phantom limb pain if not adequately managed. Multimodal analgesic strategies have demonstrated benefits in reducing pain intensity and opioid consumption, with intravenous (IV) lidocaine emerging as a therapeutic alternative due to its antihyperalgesic effects and modulation of central sensitization.

We present the case of a 77-year-old male patient with a 20-year history of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and a 15-year history of systemic arterial hypertension (SAH), non-smoker, with a history of alcohol consumption during youth (abstinent for the past 15 years), diagnosed with Texas stage III diabetic foot requiring supracondylar amputation of the left lower limb. Anesthetic management included spinal anesthesia with ropivacaine and fentanyl, placement of an epidural catheter without additional anesthetic use, and continuous IV lidocaine infusion at 1 mg/kg/h during the intraoperative period as part of a multimodal protocol. The patient remained hospitalized for 10 days and was discharged on postoperative day three.

Pain control was effective, with a maximum visual analog scale (VAS) score of 4/10 in the post-anesthesia care unit and no significant need for rescue analgesia. During outpatient follow-up, no phantom limb pain or residual neuropathic pain was documented. IV lidocaine contributed to adequate analgesia, reduced opioid requirements, and favorable functional recovery.

This case suggests that IV lidocaine infusion in the setting of major amputations may be an effective strategy within a multimodal analgesic approach, even in patients with significant comorbidities.

KEYWORDS: Lower limb amputation; Lidocaine; Regional anesthesia; Postoperative pain; Type 2 diabetes mellitus

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INTRODUCTION

Lower limb amputation is a highly nociceptive procedure frequently associated with severe postoperative pain and an increased risk of chronic and phantom limb pain if effective analgesic management is not implemented (1–3). The prevalence of non-traumatic amputations in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) has increased globally due to the higher incidence of peripheral neuropathy and peripheral vascular disease, with diabetic foot being one of the leading causes of amputation in this population (2,8). In Mexico,

complications related to the diabetic foot and associated amputations continue to represent a major public health challenge, negatively impacting quality of life and healthcare costs (1,2).

Adequate perioperative pain control in major amputations is essential to improve clinical and functional outcomes, as well as to reduce complications associated with intensive opioid use (3,4,9). Multimodal analgesic strategies combine regional techniques, intravenous adjuvants, and other pharmacological agents to modulate nociceptive responses and limit central

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sensitization, which contributes to chronic pain development (4,5,7). Within this framework, intravenous (IV) lidocaine has been studied for its antihyperalgesic, anti-inflammatory, and nociceptive-modulating effects, showing favorable outcomes in various major surgical procedures (6,7,10).

However, detailed clinical evidence regarding its specific use in major amputations among patients with significant comorbidities, such as T2DM and arterial hypertension, remains limited. Therefore, we describe the anesthetic and analgesic approach in a patient with these characteristics undergoing supracondylar amputation, with particular emphasis on IV lidocaine as part of a multimodal analgesic strategy.

CASE REPORT

A 77-year-old male patient with a medical history of type 2 diabetes mellitus for 20 years, treated with metformin 850 mg every 12 hours and insulin glargine 20 IU every 24 hours, and systemic arterial hypertension for 15 years, treated with losartan 50 mg every 24 hours. He was a non-smoker with a history of alcohol consumption during youth, including episodes of intoxication, discontinued 15 years prior. Additional comorbidities included diabetic nephropathy, multifactorial anemia, and diabetic retinopathy.

The patient was admitted due to complications related to left diabetic foot, classified as Texas stage III, with clinical and imaging findings consistent with deep infection and severe vascular compromise. After multidisciplinary evaluation by vascular surgery, internal medicine, and anesthesiology teams, urgent supracondylar amputation of the left lower limb was indicated.

Left supracondylar amputation was performed under combined regional anesthesia, using spinal anesthesia with ropivacaine 11.25 mg plus fentanyl 25 µg. An epidural catheter was additionally placed as a safety measure in case of surgical prolongation or need for supplementary analgesia; however, it was not used due to adequate anesthetic coverage throughout the procedure.

As part of a multimodal analgesic protocol, continuous IV lidocaine infusion was initiated at a dose of 1 mg/kg/h, with a total administered dose of 163 mg during the intraoperative period. Surgical time was 2 hours and 16 minutes. Anesthetic monitoring was standard (type I), with spontaneous ventilation and no requirement for supplemental oxygen upon leaving the operating room.

The patient remained hemodynamically stable throughout the procedure, with no adverse events related known to the anesthetic technique or IV lidocaine administration.

POSTOPERATIVE PAIN CONTROL

Postoperative analgesic management was highly effective. In the post-anesthesia care unit (PACU), the patient reported a maximum VAS score of 4/10. According to the Campbell pain scale, pain was described as mild, without significant

functional impairment and without the need for immediate rescue analgesia.

Postoperative comfort indices were favorable, with RASS 0, Ramsay 2, and Bromage 4 at PACU discharge. During hospitalization, no pain exacerbations or high opioid requirements were observed.

The patient remained hospitalized for a total of 10 days and was discharged on postoperative day three. During outpatient follow-up, no phantom limb pain, neuropathic pain, or dysesthesias were documented, suggesting adequate control of central sensitization from the perioperative period.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This case report was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for the procedures described and for the use of clinical information for academic and scientific purposes, always ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of personal data.

The study did not involve any interventions beyond those established as part of the patient's standard clinical care. The report was reviewed and approved by the Research Committee (CI-2025-048-HGC) and the Research Ethics Committee (CEI-2025-048-HGC) of the Hospital General de Cancún.

DISCUSSION

The anesthetic management of patients with chronic comorbidities such as type 2 diabetes mellitus and systemic arterial hypertension undergoing major surgery represents a challenge due to increased risks of hemodynamic instability, exacerbated inflammatory responses, and perioperative metabolic complications. In this context, multimodal analgesia and regional anesthesia techniques remain fundamental to optimizing clinical outcomes.

Multiple studies have demonstrated that neuraxial anesthesia, particularly with epidural catheter placement, allows improved modulation of the neuroendocrine stress response, reduces general anesthetic and opioid requirements, and promotes faster recovery of gastrointestinal function and early mobilization (1–3). In the present case, the epidural catheter was not a complementary measure but an integral component of the anesthetic plan, facilitating systemic lidocaine administration as an analgesic and anti-inflammatory strategy.

Both intravenous and epidural lidocaine have shown benefits beyond analgesia, including antihyperalgesic effects, opioid-sparing properties, reduced incidence of postoperative ileus, and improved pain control in major abdominal and pelvic surgeries (4–6). In patients with T2DM, these effects are particularly relevant, as minimizing pain and surgical stress contributes to improved glycemic control and reduced infectious complications.

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Clinical case reports and series published in anesthesiology journals indicate that the combination of regional anesthesia and lidocaine infusion is associated with shorter hospital stays and earlier discharge, without increased adverse events, provided therapeutic dosing and appropriate monitoring are maintained (7–9). In this case, clinical evolution was favorable, with hospital discharge on day ten and postoperative discharge on day three, without anesthetic or neurological complications attributable to epidural catheter use or lidocaine infusion.

This approach aligns with current evidence supporting the use of continuous regional techniques as part of enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) protocols, even in patients with multiple comorbidities (10).

CONCLUSION

The use of an epidural catheter as an integral component of the anesthetic plan, combined with intravenous lidocaine infusion, proved to be a safe and effective strategy for pain control and modulation of the surgical stress response in a patient with T2DM and systemic arterial hypertension. This approach enabled favorable postoperative recovery, adequate hemodynamic stability, and early discharge, supporting its usefulness in the context of major surgery in patients with chronic comorbidities.

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